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**Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning:
FEMaLe**

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Legislation

Legislation H2020 Framework Programme – Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ 347, 20.12.2013, p. 104).

H2020 Specific Programme – Council Decision 2013/743/EU of 3 December 2013 establishing the Specific Programme Implementing Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 965).

Rules for Participation (RfP) – Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 of December 2013 laying down the rules for the participation and dissemination in Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p.81).

Financial Regulation (FR) – Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the European Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

Rules of Application (RAP) – Commission Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1268/2012 of 29 October 2012 on the rules of application of 1 Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p.1).

1. ALL WP IMPACT MONITORING & ASSESSMENT REPORTS

This report covers the *Impact Monitoring and Assessment (IMA)* across all work packages (WPs) in the FEMaLe project, covering months 31-42. The IMA report includes the following sections:

- 1) FEMaLe Pulse Checks,
- 2) Impact Case workshop results, and
- 3) Half Double Evaluation.

The report also provides an overview of the project's overall impact from the start of the project until now, as well as a description of how tools from the Half Double Methodology have guided and directed the project towards its ultimate goals.

The Half Double Methodology was implemented from the beginning of the project, with WP1's primary task being to introduce it to the remaining work packages. This ensured a common approach, language, and collaboration across the project.

At the end of the report, you will find an overview of the overall value creation achieved by implementing the Half Double Methodology into the FEMaLe project.

2. FEMaLe Pulse Checks

The *FEMaLe Pulse Checks* are online surveys consisting of six questions from the Half Double Methodology, continuously sent to all project members. These Pulse Checks navigate the project by providing insights into the satisfaction of the project members, creating the necessary insights backed up by data over time. This drives a focused dialogue amongst key stakeholders, ensuring continuous focus on impact, energizing working conditions, collaboration as well as both personal and professional development within the project. The FEMaLe Pulse Checks are conducted through the SurveyXact encrypted software. First, Pulse Check results from August 2023 to June 2024 will be presented, followed by results from the entire project period.

FEMALE BENEFICIARY (N=17)	RESPONSES (N=30)	PRIMARY <u>WPs</u> (N=10)
Aarhus Universitet	Y (5)	3,8,10
Aarhus Universitetshospital	Y (1)	6,7
European Society for Quality and Patient Safety in General Practice/Family Medicine	Y (1)	1,9
Semmelweis Egyetem	Y (3)	5,6,7
The Chancellor, Masters, And Scholars of The University of Oxford	Y (2)	4,9
Surgar	Y (2)	6,7
Rigas Tehniska Universitate	Y (1)	4,6,7
Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	Y (2)	5
Istanbul Avrupa Arastirmalari Dernegi	Y (1)	2
Precisionlife Ltd	Y (1)	4
Yourcode Lab Informatikai, Szolgaltato Es Tanacsado Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag	Y (1)	5,8
The University Court of The University of Aberdeen	Y (2)	3
Correlate As	Y (2)	10
Nemanja Todic Preduzetnik Web Bay	Y (1)	9
Egyutt Konnyebb Noi Egeszsegert Alapitvany	Y (1)	2,9
The University of Edinburgh	Y (2)	3
Aalborg University	Y (2)	4

17 of 17 (100%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries responded to Pulse Check electronic questionnaire at least once.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: August 2023

14 out of 30 FEMaLers (47%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 12 of 17 (71%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 93% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,5).
- 71% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,2).
- 79% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,1).
- 79% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,1).
- 93% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,6).
- 79% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,4).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: October 2023

17 out of 30 FEMaLers (57%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 13 of 17 (76%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 88% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,4).
- 71% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,2).
- 76% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (-0,1).
- 71% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,0 of 5 (-).
- 88% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,6).
- 76% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,4).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: December 2023

16 out of 30 FEMaLers (53%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 13 of 17 (76%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 100% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,6 of 5 (+0,6).
- 100% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,6).
- 87% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,1).
- 81% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,1).
- 100% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,6 of 5 (+0,8).
- 100% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,6 of 5 (+0,8).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: February 2024

15 out of 30 FEMaLers (50%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 12 of 17 (71%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 87% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,4).
- 80% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,2).
- 80% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (-0,1).
- 80% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,1).
- 93% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,4 of 5 (+0,6).
- 87% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: April 2024

17 out of 30 FEMaLers (57%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 13 of 17 (76%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 88% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,5).
- 88% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,3).
- 88% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (-0,1).
- 82% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,1).
- 82% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).
- 82% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,1 of 5 (+0,3).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

FEMaLe Pulse Check Results: June 2024

17 out of 30 FEMaLers (50%) replied to the Pulse Check electronic questionnaire through SurveyXact, representing 14 of 17 (82%) FEMaLe Beneficiaries, upon which we can draw the following conclusion:

- 100% are confident that their current work create impact for FEMaLe; average score 4,6 of 5 (+0,6).
- 82% believe that they deliver and collaborate effectively in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,3).
- 84% are having fun and get energy out of working in FEMaLe; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,2).
- 84% are getting the support and feedback they need working in FEMaLe; average score 4,2 of 5 (+0,2).
- 88% are developing personally and professionally working in FEMaLe; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,7).
- 88% are convinced that FEMaLe focuses on early impact creation; average score 4,5 of 5 (+0,7).

Score compared to baseline level indicated in brackets.

The overall impact and assessment summary can be found in *Appendix 1*.

Impact Monitoring and Assessment Summary, 06 2021 to 06 2024

This section presents the development over time based on each of the six pulse check questions from the first data collection in June 2021 to the latest data collection in June 2024.

An additional question 4 was implemented in January 2023.

Summery

The figures suggest that the up to 40 FEMaLers employed in the project, representing the 17 FEMaLe Beneficiaries, believe their current work is creating impact for the project, contributing to both personal and professional development, and that the FEMaLe Project is executed more effectively and with a greater focus on impact compared to other projects.

Project members report an average score of 88% when asked if they are confident that their current work creates impact for the project (*Q1*). Also, the average score was 87% when asked if they are having fun and energy working in the project (*Q3*).

However, at the beginning of 2023, there was a noticeable decrease in the project members experience of delivering and collaborating effectively in the project (*Q2*). In January 2023, this only resulted in a score of 56%, and in May 2023, the score was just 65%. In response to this, proactive mitigation actions were initiated to address the issue and to avoid poor performance.

These actions appeared to re-establish the project members' perception of delivering and collaborating effectively in the project based on subsequent results, including a 100% score on the same question in December 2023 (*Q2*). Overall, FEMaLe Project continues to perform well above its baseline levels.

3. Impact Case Workshop report

The *Impact Case workshops results* provide an overview of how to transform project deliverables into smaller sub-goals. The description includes a hierarchy of goals for the desired impacts and the behavioural impacts that are needed to realize the overall impact. The Impact Case workshop results report contains all WP Impact Cases with accompanying key performance indicators (KPIs).

The purpose is to give FEMaLe partners an overview, monitor their progress, and help them realize impact faster. The workshops took place in Q3 2023 and were regularly revisited at FEMaLe consortium meetings to discuss and review the status.

In the report, Impact Cases are color-coded: blue indicates completed tasks, while yellow signifies tasks that are ‘in progress’, ‘ongoing’ or ‘not yet completed’.

WP1

Impact Case: WP1 Q3 2023 - Q4 2024			
Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Create impact case workshops to monitor value creation in all FEMaLe work packages	10 impact cases produced	Completed	
Evaluate use of Half Double in FEMaLe	10 Half Double evaluations produced	Completed	
Monitor stakeholder satisfaction in FEMaLe	8 Pulse Checks conducted	Ongoing	So far, we have collected 5 pulse checks. The remaining will be collected before Q4 2024
Submit D1.9 IMA reporting	D1.9 quality checked by PMO	Completed	Submitted
FEMaLe overall value creation summarised	All work packages describe total value created during FEMaLe's duration.		Should we involve 'Horizon Results Booster' to achieve this?
Continue documenting use of Half Double	1 book chapter delivered Q4, 2023	Completed	Book chapter submitted Feb24
Continue documenting use of Half Double	1 scientific article published Q4, 2024	Ongoing	Scientific article will be submitted Q1 2025.

WP2

Impact Case: WP2

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Increase the accessibility of D2.2	Create an action plan for dissemination	Ongoing	Stared with the elaboration of a draft considering D9.1, 9.2 9.3. 100% digital
Increase the accessibility of D2.3	Create an action plan for dissemination	Ongoing	Stared with the elaboration of a draft considering D9.1, 9.2 9.3.
Increase the accessibility of D2.4	Create an action plan for dissemination	Ongoing	Stared with the elaboration of a draft considering D9.1, 9.2 9.3.
Create FEMaLe recommendations to policymakers, involving advisors	Online workshop conducted. Decide on repository for FAIR data sharing	Not started yet	Request cooperation by partners on suggested platforms. <u>Candidate platfroms</u> : OpenAIRE, Zenodo etc. <u>Candidate supports</u> : Policy brief, coordination and support action programme, ect.
Produce commentary article	Create first draft article based on our current notes, data and ideas.	Ongoing	First draft created

WP3

Impact Case: WP3

Q3 2023 + Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Submission of manuscript on the consensus study Q4 2023	Manuscript submitted to scientific journal	Completed	Submitted to Fertility and Sterility 1st May 2024
Linkage between survey data and DK registry data Q4 2023	Linkage at Statistics Denmark	Completed	The data was linked December 2023
Update of Dk registry data Q4 2023	Registry data updated at Statistics Denmark	Completed	The data was updated December 2023
Analyses for manuscript on work years lost Q4 2023	Data management and analyses done	Completed	Data management complete and analysis almost complete, but very time consuming due to large
Data management for manuscript on distribution of symptoms in Dk Q4 2023	Survey data linked with registries and data management prepared	Completed	Data linked and data management and analyses completed
Data management for manuscript on DK phenotype description Q4 2023	Data management done	Ongoing	Data management completed and analyse ongoing
Data management on CPRD data for study on UK prevalence of endometriosis like symptoms Q4 2023	Data management done	Completed	Primary and secondary care linked data received Dec 2023, data management complete

Impact Case: WP4

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Complete Task 4.3.2	Finalise data processing agreements between Aalborg and Oxford.	In progress	draft agreement, third-party security assessment ongoing
Complete Task 4.3.3	Genotyping and biomarker profiling of samples from miENDO and ENDOX cohorts and receipt of data.	Completed	
Complete Task 4.3.4	Relevant information for characterization of endometriosis subgroups identified from Danish registries in collaboration with WP3.	Completed	
Complete Task 4.3.5	Design analysis plan for analysis of the phenotypic, genotypic and proteomic data from miENDO and ENDOX.	Completed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Possible clusters for cohort 3 2) 37 clusters 3) GWAS extended clusters 4) High low FRS 5) unsupervised clustering from proteins
Complete Task 4.3.6	To determine what characterises the endometriosis sub-types following the analysis plan	Ongoing	we are currently investigating each individual data set, awaiting third-party security assessment allowing us to merge the two datasets
Complete Task 4.3.7	Investigate possible access to an additional dataset from Harvard University	Completed	Whereas access to individual genotypes from Harvard will not be possible, we may be able to ask the Harvard team to run short, targeted analyses (e.g. specific genotype-phenotype associations) and for them to share summary stats with us, based on the analysis plan to be drafted. This is being explored.
Complete Task 4.3.8	Write the milestone report for Task 4.3.	In progress	Extended to 30th June 2024
Submit D4.3	Submit report D4.3.	Pending	Extended to 30th June 2024
Reply to reviewers' comment R7 (Scientific output)	peer-review academic output	In progress	One of the important focuses for WP4 is indeed on peer-reviewed academic output in the coming period. Note our first paper in <i>Nature Genetics</i> , as part of a larger collaboration, published in March 2023.
Reply to reviewers' comment R8	Identify what data are going to be shared	In progress	Nilufer has volunteered to be part of a data management group, but we are unsure how this is moving forward, who else will be on it, etc?
Complete Task 4.4.1	Prototyping of CRS tool (combinatorial risk scores)	In progress	preparing more SNP genotype combinations for better stratification
Complete Task 4.4.2	Decision on the best triage risk scores of endometriosis patients	In progress	CRS tool extended with genes and biological mechanisms
Complete Task 4.4.3	Prototyping CDS tool including biological subtypes	In progress	CRS tool can be extended with genes, mechanisms, subtypes or other information later in the project
Complete Task 4.4.4	Specification of CDS tool (core OEM engine)	In progress	To be completed Q3 2024 final product design
Complete Task 4.4.5	Software implementation of CDS tool based on specifications	In progress	To be completed Q3 2024
Submit D4.4	Submit report D4.4.	In progress	Due Oct 2024

WP5

Impact Case: WP5

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Submit D5.5	Report has been co-produced and quality checked before end of the year	Completed	
Improve the number of completed questionnaires, incl. healthy users	Lucy App launched in Denmark and Sweden before Q4 2023.	In progress	Launched in Denmark in Q 2024
Promote Lucy app in Denmark and Sweden	Recruitment plans produced in partnership with patient associations	In progress	Completed in Denmark
Finalise Lucy app the Danish version	Danish translations validated, incl. Lucy app content and used questionnaires	Completed	
Finalise Lucy app the Swedish version	Swedish translations validated, incl. Lucy app content and used questionnaires	Completed	
Explore the optimal data utilisation from questionnaire and lifestyle and dietary modules	Discuss data quantity and quality	In progress	The article detailing the study protocol has been published
Participate in national conferences	Dora and Attila will participate in a congress in Hungary (6th Meeting of Young Endoscopic Gynecologists)	Completed	
Participate in international conferences	Attila will participate in conferences and design impactful presentations	Completed	EEL congress in 2024 SEUD masterclass, Budapest Nov 20-Dec 02 7th European congress on Endometriosis, Romania June 6-8
Exploitation of Lucy	Share data from Lucy users by connecting survey fillings with user data	Completed	
Reply to review comment R3	A respectful response clarifying the misunderstanding has been submitted	In progress	
Reply to review comment R4	Two research experiments to engage Lucy users more have been carried out	In progress	

WP6
Impact Case: WP6
Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Integration of Algorithm into AR software	Visualize boxes on offline images	Completed	
Submit D6.4	Deliverable quality checked by PMO	Completed	
More scientific outputs	1 journal paper on neural network architectures comparison submitted	Ongoing	First draft is ready
Preclinical validation (questionnaire-based)	Results for at least 10 surgeons	Ongoing	First results has been presented
More scientific outputs	1 journal paper on ontology submitted	Completed	
Data management plan: Final	Agree on how to share data publicly	Completed	
Reply to review comment R8 (FAIR)	Share 10% (1 lesion detection) of neural model for lesion detection	Completed	

WP7

Impact Case: WP7

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Submit D7.3	Deliverable quality checked by PMO	Completed	Submitted
Describe detailed development process from now (Sept 2023) and until Sept 2024	Road map to unfold process produced	Completed	
Pre-clinical Validation	Results for at least 10 surgeons	Ongoing	Planned to be a questionnaire based evaluation for 10 surgeons to evaluate the algorithm
Integration to the software	Visualization of incision boundaries	Ongoing	The software is already integrated and works as expected
More scientific outputs	Master's thesis re-written into another paper (journal or conference paper)	Ongoing	To be submitted in Sep/Oct 2024
Submit 7.4	Deliverable quality checked by PMO At least 1 fps to be considered real-time	Ongoing	No later than September 2024
Exploitation of results	Road map covering scientific outputs as well as IIP management plan produced	Ongoing	<small>To be done no later than Dec 2023 Legal protection of assets Software, data, and model Pre-clinical interviews and clinical validation will reveal the real value of the project and its results, we can oriente the future developments and plan to build IP in the way One congress on DDD Surgical AI day, and hopefully a journal</small>
Increase annotations	At least 10,000 annotated data	Ongoing	

WP8

Impact Case: WP8

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Submit D8.2	Translate the English version to Hungarian. Proofread both versions.	Completed	
D8.3, part 1 of 3	Create and launch the publicly available, finished version of MY-ENDO in LearnDash	Ongoing	Danish version is still up and running. We shall explore possibilities to extend the localisations to support HU and EN.
D8.3, part 2 of 3	Finish the content, design, layout in the learn dash MY-ENDO version	Ongoing	Responsible: Karina. Norbert shall get admin access to help with the localisations.
Submit D8.3, part 3 of 3	Deep link to the LearnDash version of MY-ENDO from Lucy	Ongoing	Responsible: Norbert. Dependent on Task 2-3, will be trivial afterwards.
Pilot-test new MY-ENDO research platform	Set up secure phone, e-mail and zoom-link for contact with RCT participants	Completed	The setup for the pilot test is finished, the tests are ongoing with 50 patients currently.
Recruit up to 200 patient for the RCT	Pilot test of MY-ENDO completed	Ongoing	ALH and patient association onboarded. We will start as soon as Task 5 is completed, we do not expect to recruit 200 patient, due to lack of time and platform delay.
Reply to reviewers' comment R6 (risk assessment), part 1	AU Data Management Unit has fully explained need for another platform	Completed	
Reply to reviewers' comment R6 (risk assessment), part 2	AU Data Management Unit has explained the longed delay delivering	Completed	
Reply to reviewers' comment R7 (dissemination via peer-reviewed articles), part 1	Nina's feasibility study article accepted for peer-review	In progress	Not accepted yet to the selected journals.
Reply to reviewers' comment R7 (dissemination via peer-reviewed articles), part 2	Research article for the study protocol accepted for peer-review	In progress	ETA depends on higher priority tasks in WP
Reply to reviewers' comment R7 (dissemination via peer-reviewed articles), part 3	We make best use of the delay and will add objective data collection to the study	In progress	A collaboration with Garmin is on the way, currently the data management office evaluates the plan.
Build the electronic questionnaire in Redcap/SurveyXact	Pilot test and adjust the electronic questionnaire	Completed	

WP9

Impact Case: WP9

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Assist SURGAR and SWU with collecting data for D9.6, D97, D9.9 and D.9.10	Create a feedback system to get an overview of the projects output, contributions and results.	To be validated	
Create SoMe content plan for 2024	Create SoMe content plan for 2024 which reuses previously posted FEMaLe content, as well as content from relevant	Completed	Plan is created and we are executing it. We had sufficient amount of new materials for 2024
Promotion of Lucy app	Create a promotion plan together with other relevant FEMaLe partners	Completed	Plan is created, and multiple actions are already completed
Regularly update our SoMe reach	Continue counting and labelling SoMe posts in a fixed rhythm	Ongoing	We continuously update our SoMe reach in a fixed rhythm
Improve our contact with other patient associations	Enables others outside the project to contact us and contribute with content through the FEMaLe website.	Ongoing	We are engaged with German association with a large social media followers base. Also we are in contact with Dutch association
Post our scheduled SoMe content	Continue posting the Endometriosis glossary and partner promotion (consider repeat partner promotion)	Ongoing	Partner promotion is completed. Glossary campaign will continue.
Prepare #Endomarch content for 2024	Reuse existing videos developed by WorldWideEndoMarch	Completed	Content for #Endomarch prepared and well executed
Create content plan for newsletter	Increase visualisation of dissemination	Completed	We cancelled the newsletter due to low engagement and the resources will be redirected to improve the website
Target recommendations for specific stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Produce guidelines for public health authorities to support implementation. - Engage policy makers through strategy plan and patient associations. 	Ongoing	<p>We are in planning phase of this task, although a number of actions are already taken.</p>

WP10

Impact Case: WP10

Q3 2023 - Q4 2024

Task	KPI	Status	Comment
Submit D10.9 Progress monitoring (Responsible: AU)	Inputs per ongoing task for all 10 work package collected.	Completed	Approved by EC 26 april 2024
Submit D10.12 Progress monitoring (Responsible: AU)	Inputs per ongoing task for all 10 work package collected.	Ongoing	Will be submitted in Aug 2024
Submit D10.24 Data-driven digital management platform (Responsible: Correlate)	Prioritise next development project(s). Action Plan produced.	Completed	Approved by EC 26 april 2024
Submit D10.25 Data-driven digital management platform (Responsible: Correlate)	Prioritise final development project(s). Action Plan produced.	Ongoing	Defining roadmap priorities for Q4 2023 + 2024 Will be submitted in Nov 2024
Submit D10.28 Knowledge management guidelines & brief (Responsible: Correlate)	Principles for and value creation of knowledge sharing described.	Completed	Submitted
Submit D10.29 Knowledge management guidelines & brief (Responsible: Correlate)	Principles for and value creation of knowledge sharing described.	Ongoing	Will be submitted in Nov 2024
Submit D10.32 Final DMP (Responsible: AU)	All FEMaLe partners have been involved in sharing data management inputs.	Ongoing	Will be submitted in Oct 2024
Create an action plan for correlate (Responsible: Correlate)	Rethinking Correlate's vision in the last phase of the FEMaLe project	Ongoing	To be discussed with Correlate team
Host 3 webinars with FEMaLes (Responsible: Correlate)	Invite FEMaLers to attend a webinar on the use of AI in Correlate	To be initiated	Postponed due to AI improvements
Develop a risk assessment plan in FEMaLe (Responsible: AU)	Final risk assessment plan co-created using Miro by FEMaLe WP Leaders.	Completed	Done at most recent FEMaLe Executive Board meeting
Create action plan for archiving all FEMaLe documents (Responsible: Correlate + AU)	Clarify in PMO how we will archive data, even after the project has ended, using correlates expertise for archiving.	Ongoing	To be discussed with Correlate team

Summery

The Impact Cases reveal that out of a total of 93 defined sub-tasks, 40 have been completed already and 49 is 'in progress' or marked as 'ongoing' tasks. This result is much expected, as the remaining sub-tasks will be completed in the final phase of the project and no later than December 2024.

Especially, WP2 and WP6 have activities that involve ongoing data collection that will continue throughout the duration of the project. This also applies to WP9, which has ongoing social media activities, where we continuously update our reach, improve contact with patient associations, and post our scheduled SoMe content, which will continue into the final project period.

During this project period, we have had a dedicated focus on *impact* rather than merely on the deliverables, aligned with the Half Double Methodology. This has enabled us to reach further and wider with our results, generating early impact already during the FEMaLe Project, which has been particularly beneficial for the project in its final phase.

Deviations from the Impact Cases and KPIs co-created by each of the ten FEMaLe work packages as well as relevant mitigating actions will be unfolded in the deliverable D10.12 Progress monitoring, quality control and brief M32, which is due 31 August 2024.

4. Constructive Half Double Evaluation

The following section presents the results of the Constructive Half Double Evaluation conducted at the individual WP level within the FEMaLe project. This evaluation is the final one in a series of four evaluations conducted throughout the project.

The aim of the evaluation is to gain insights into how each WP incorporates the HDM, with the objective to improve and validate project activities, while tracking the usage of the tools over time. The data provides an overview of which tools the WP are confident working with, highlighting the tools to focus on using even more. Moreover, it offers systematised data, which we can use to observe the development of the tool usage from the Half Double Methodology over time. In Appendix 2, a visual illustration of the results from all four evaluations can be found.

The evaluation draws on a multidimensional framework and consists of 17 questions related to the three core elements of the project methodology: *Impact*, *Flow*, and *Leadership*. These questions referred to the nine Half Double practices.

Participants were required to assign a score ranging from 0 to 4, with 1 representing low application and 4 indicating high application of the practice (0 indicate that the practice is not applicable). An average score was used as a threshold to determine whether the WP is considered to have implemented the HDM (>2.5: utilising the HDM, <2.5: not utilising the HDM).

The evaluation was conducted through an online questionnaire using SurveyXact, an encrypted survey software.

Table 2 shows the results and progress in the application of the method.

Table 2: Progress in the use of Half Double practices, from the 1st evaluation (baseline) to 4th evaluation

	Impact			Co-location	Flow		Leadership			Average score
	Impact case	Impact solution design	Pulse check		Visual planning	Rhythm in key events	Active ownership approach	Collaborative leadership approach	Reflective and adaptive mindset	
WP1										
1 st evaluation	4	2	4	1	4	3	1	4	3	2,89
2 nd evaluation	4	4	4	1	4	4	1	4	4	3,33
3 rd evaluation	4	4	4	2	3	4	0	4	4	3,22
4 th evaluation	4	4	4	4 (+2)	3	3 (+1)	4 (+4)	4	4	3,89 (+0,67)
WP2										
1 st evaluation	1	3	1	4	3	1	1	4	4	2,44
2 nd evaluation	3	3	1	4	2	3	1	4	4	2,78
3 rd evaluation	Missing data									
4 th evaluation	2 (-1)	2 (-1)	3 (+2)	1 (-3)	3 (+1)	3	4 (+3)	3 (-1)	3 (-1)	2,67 (-0,11)

WP3										
1 st evaluation	1	2	2	1	2	3	4	3	2	2,22
2 nd evaluation	3	2	2	1	2	2	4	3	2	2,33
3 rd evaluation	0	0	2	2	2	3	1	1	2	1,44
4 th evaluation	2 (+2)	2 (+2)	2	3 (+1)	3 (+1)	3	2 (+1)	2 (+1)	2	2,33 (+0,89)
WP4										
1 st evaluation	3	3	2	1	2	4	3	4	3	2,78
2 nd evaluation	2	3	2	2	3	4	3	4	3	2,89
3 rd evaluation	0	0	0	2	0	2	2	0	4	1,11
4 th evaluation	2 (+2)	3 (+3)	3 (+3)	2	2 (+2)	4 (+2)	3 (+3)	3 (+3)	3 (-1)	2,78 (+1,67)
WP5										
1 st evaluation	2	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	2	3,00
2 nd evaluation	3	4	2	4	3	4	4	4	2	3,33
3 rd evaluation	4	4	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	3,78
4 th evaluation	2 (-2)	3 (-1)	3 (-1)	1 (-3)	3 (-1)	3 (-1)	3 (-1)	4	3 (-1)	2,78 (-1,00)

WP6+7											
1 st evaluation	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	3	2,67	
2 nd evaluation	2	4	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	2,67	
3 rd evaluation	2	4	4	2	3	4	2	2	2	2,78	
4 th evaluation	3 (+1)	3 (+1)	4	3 (+1)	3	4	3 (+1)	2	3 (+1)	3,11 (+0,33)	
WP8											
1 st evaluation	3	4	1	1	3	2	4	-	4	2,44	
2 nd evaluation	3	4	3	3	2	2	4	3	4	3,11	
3 rd evaluation	4	4	4	0	2	4	4	4	4	3,33	
4 th evaluation	2 (-2)	4	3 (+1)	1 (+1)	3 (+1)	4	4	4	3 (+1)	3,11 (-0,22)	
WP9											
1 st evaluation	2	3	1	1	4	2	2	4	3	2,44	
2 nd evaluation	2	4	1	1	4	4	2	4	3	2,78	
3 rd evaluation	2	4	2	2	4	4	4	4	4	3,33	
4 th evaluation	4 (+2)	4	3 (+1)	3 (+1)	4	4	4	4	4	3,78 (+0,45)	

WP10										
1 st evaluation	4	3	4	1	4	4	4	4	4	3,56
2 nd evaluation	4	4	3	2	4	4	3	4	4	3,56
3 rd evaluation	2	4	2	3	4	4	4	4	4	3,44
4 th evaluation	3 (+1)	4	3 (+1)	3	4	4	2 (-2)	4	4	3,44

Summery

Table 2 illustrates the progression in the adoption of the Half Double practices from the initial baseline score to the fourth evaluation of the WPs in the project. WP6 and WP7 are merged in the evaluations, as they work closely together and as several of their tasks are comparable.

The results from the fourth evaluation reveal that 8 out of 9 WPs have an average score of >2.5 , indicating successful implementation of HDM. This marks an improvement since the last evaluation.

Although WP3 has not fully implemented the HDM, with a score of 2.33, it shows significant progress with an increase of +0.89, compared to the previous evaluation. This indicates that they have become even better at applying the practices from HDM.

The results show no systematic difference in the use of HDM across different types of WPs.

The evaluation also provides an overview of the FEMaLe project's use of HDM throughout the entire project period, from the first to the final project year. This offers a comprehensive, systematised overview of the FEMaLe Project's use of HDM over time, highlighting the projects strengths and weaknesses and allowing us to track the development.

The latest constructive evaluation confirms that the FEMaLe project has successfully implemented the Half Double Methodology, with almost all work packages (8 out of 9) consistently utilising and making use of the methods from the Half Double. Appendix 2 provides a visual illustration of the four evaluations from each work package, highlighting the development over time.

5. How the Half Double Methodology Contributed to Creating and Enhancing Impact in FEMaLe

FEMaLe project has gained valuable experience from more than 3.5 years of implementing Half Double Methodology. During this time, the work packages have effectively utilized various tools provided by the methodology.

The Half Double Methodology has helped us to create value and promote impact in FEMaLe. *Impact* is one of the core elements of the methodology, providing direct tools that can be implemented and used in the project.

In WP1, we have particularly utilized *Impact Cases*, *Pulse Checks*, and *Constructive Evaluations*, as described in the previous sections. These tools have helped us create an overview of the entire project, benefiting both the individual project members and the project management office (PMO). Together, the three Half Double tools have proven helpful in creating and promoting early impact in the FEMaLe Project. They provide useful for optimizing our internal communication, offering a shared and common language that enhances understanding across diverse backgrounds, topics, and disciplines, thus improving our collaboration.

By using Half Double, we have collected systematised data, allowing us to track progress in relation to our KPIs and the development of Half Double tools over time. This element has been particularly valuable for FEMaLe, as it allows us to quickly assist the individual work packages when needed. This approach has contributed to early value creation and enhanced project outcomes.

Overall, the implementation, utilization, and insights derived from our specific use of Half Double have significantly contributed to realising impact in FEMaLe. Particularly, it has helped FEMaLe to reduce complexity in our large research and innovation project, reduced time to benefit and impact, and established a structure and overview of project activities.

6. Appendix

Appendix 1: Impact monitoring and assessment summary, Q3 2023 to Q2 2024

Average score	08 2023 (n=14)	10 2023 (n=17)	12 2023 (n=16)	02 2024 (n=15)	04 2024 (n=17)	06 2024 (n=17)
Question 1	4.5 (+0.5)	4.4 (+0.4)	4.6 (+0.6)	4.4 (+0.4)	4.5 (+0.5)	4.6 (+0.6)
Question 2	4.1 (+0.2)	4.1 (+0.2)	4.5 (+0.6)	4.1 (+0.2)	4.2 (+0.3)	4.2 (+0.3)
Question 3	4.4 (+0.1)	4.2 (-0.1)	4.4 (+0.1)	4.2 (-0.1)	4.2 (-0.1)	4.5 (+0.2)
Question 4	4.1 (+0.1)	4.0 (-)	4.1 (+0.1)	4.1 (+0.1)	4.1 (+0.1)	4.2 (+0.2)
Question 5	4.4 (+0.6)	4.4 (+0.6)	4.6 (+0.8)	4.4 (+0.6)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.5 (+0.7)
Question 6	4.2 (+0.4)	4.2 (+0.4)	4.6 (+0.8)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.1 (+0.3)	4.5 (+0.7)
Average mean	4.28	4.22	4.47	4.22	4.20	4.42

Positive score	08 2023	10 2023	12 2023	02 2024	04 2024	06 2024
Question 1	93%	88%	100%	87%	88%	100%
Question 2	71%	71%	100%	80%	88%	82%
Question 3	79%	76%	87%	80%	88%	94%
Question 4	79%	71%	81%	80%	82%	94%
Question 5	93%	88%	100%	93%	82%	88%
Question 6	79%	76%	100%	87%	82%	88%
Average mean	82.3%	78.3%	94.7%	84.5%	85.0%	91.0%

The Questionnaire

Question 1. Are you confident that your current work is creating impact for the project?

Question 2. Do we deliver and collaborate effectively in the project?

Question 3. Are you having fun and energy working in the project?

Question 4. Are you getting the support and feedback you need?

Question 5. Are you developing personally and professionally working in the project?

Question 6. All in all; are you convinced that this project is executed more effectively and with more focus on impact than other projects?

Appendix 2: Results from the Half Double evaluations: Spiderweb charts

The results are illustrated in spiderweb charts, divided into the nine HDM tools; the centre of the diagram corresponds to a score of 0, and the outer ring of the diagram corresponds to a score of 4:

